

LEARNING STYLES OF PRIMARY LEARNERS: BASIS FOR PROGRAM DEVELOPMENT

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Learning Styles of Primary Learners: Basis for Program Development

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Abstract

This study is concerned with the learning style of primary learners in San Manuel, District, Pangasinan Division II for SY 2023 – 2024. The study surveyed learning styles of primary learners. Primary learners preferred visual learning styles, with a smaller percentage preferring logical learning. The study found no significant difference in learning styles on academic performance across various variables. A moderate positive correlation was found between age and learning styles, but weak negative correlations were found between sex, civil status, and educational attainment. Understanding and catering to learning styles might be more crucial for students in certain divisions and national backgrounds. Visual learners can significantly improve their academic performance by incorporating visual elements into lessons. Teachers can help them grasp complex concepts, improve memory retention, and increase engagement with the material. Recognizing and accommodating the needs of visual learners is crucial for creating effective and engaging learning environments. This report emphasizes the importance of catering to diverse learning styles to promote a more inclusive and effective learning environment for all primary learners. It is also recommended that support teachers' to professional development through workshops, seminars, and conferences, and offer scholarships, grants, or financial assistance for advanced degrees or specialized training. Incorporate visual aids and techniques like mind-mapping in education, especially for subjects where visual learning is effective. Focus on diverse teaching methods to create a more engaging and productive learning environment for all students. The Visual (Spatial) Learning Style is recommended for public school teachers to improve academic performance. Further research may explore the impact of learners' learning styles on their academic performance.

Keywords: *learning style, academic performance, public schools, visual, auditory*

Introduction

In today's education, it's essential to stay informed about the various strategies and resources available for providing personalized learning experiences for our students. To differentiate our instruction effectively, we must understand our classroom's different types of learners. Differentiation involves tailoring our lessons to accommodate specific student learning styles. We can create individualized options for independent work or group students based on specific topics, areas of interest, or levels of understanding. As for resources, we can develop handouts, study guides, and worksheets and utilize various teaching strategies. One compelling example is implementing blended learning and using stations in the classroom. Through stations, teachers can design different activities where students can engage with the content in diverse ways. By structuring activities that offer various learning options for each student, we can empower students with more meaningful learning experiences and allow teachers to work with each student individually during class.

Individuals process information best through their preferred learning modes, such as visual or verbal instruction. Understanding one's learning style can benefit learners or professionals participating in development or educational opportunities, as it helps them process information effectively.

Understanding learners' learning styles is crucial for educators as it helps them tailor their teaching methods to meet their diverse needs, leading to better academic performance. Learning styles are the unique ways learners absorb, process, understand, and retain information, impacting their learning efficiency. Tailoring teaching methods to meet individual needs can improve learning outcomes.

Learning styles are distinct methods individuals use to learn effectively, affecting their ability to absorb information, understand procedures, develop competencies, and apply skills in practical settings. These styles are influenced by various theories, making it challenging for educators, scholars, and theorists to agree on the best definition and assessment of learning styles. Despite the inconsistent application of this concept, understanding one's learning style is valuable for strategic decision-making and success in pursuing training, development, and education opportunities.

Fleming (2014) claimed that visual learners prefer seeing (visual aids representing ideas using methods other than words, such as graphs, charts, diagrams, symbols, etc.). Understanding learners' learning styles is essential for improving learners' academic performance in the United States. Common learning styles include visual learners who prefer visual aids; auditory learners who prefer spoken words, kinesthetic learners who prefer hands-on activities, logical learners who prefer structured approaches, interpersonal learners who thrive in collaborative environments, and intrapersonal learners who prefer independent work. Teachers can use infographics, videos, and slideshows to cater to these learners while incorporating group discussions, lectures, and audio recordings can help them retain information better. Kinesthetic learners prefer hands-on activities, logical learners prefer structured approaches, and interpersonal learners thrive in collaborative environments. Intrapersonal learners who are self-motivated prefer independent work and self-reflection. Teachers can establish a more prosperous and diverse learning environment by incorporating these learning styles

into teaching methods. They ultimately lead to improved academic performance among students in the United States.

In Australia, Heritage (2017) said that understanding and accommodating various learning styles can significantly impact students' academic performance. These styles include Visual, Auditory, Read/Write, Kinesthetic, and Logical-Mathematical. Visual learners prefer visual aids, while auditory learners prefer listening and speaking. Kinesthetic learners prefer hands-on activities, experiments, and practical applications. Logical-mathematical learners prefer reasoning, logic, and problem-solving. To improve academic performance, educators in Australia should adopt a multi-sensory approach to teaching, incorporating diverse instructional strategies and resources that accommodate varying learning preferences.

This will ensure that all students can interact with the information in a way that best fits their needs, leading to better understanding and retention of the material.

Chuan (2018), Singaporean educators recognize the importance of addressing diverse learning styles to enhance academic performance. The four primary types of learning are auditory, visual, Read/Write, and Kinesthetic (VARK). Visual learners prefer visual aids, while Auditory learners learn best through listening and discussion. Teachers can use visuals to explain concepts, present information, and demonstrate processes. Auditory learners benefit from lectures, group discussions, and verbal explanations. Read/Write students benefit most from reading and writing, using textbooks, notes, and written descriptions. Kinesthetic learners learn best through hands-on activities, experiments, and movement. Teachers can incorporate hands-on activities, field trips, and interactive learning experiences to engage Kinesthetic learners and improve their understanding and retention of information. By being aware of and accommodating different learning preferences, Singaporean educators can create an inclusive and effective learning environment, fostering student engagement and support, ultimately leading to improved academic performance.

Schedlbauer (2019) said the German education system emphasizes critical thinking, problem-solving, and practical application, contributing to students' academic success. Critical thinking involves analyzing, evaluating, and questioning information to arrive at well-reasoned conclusions, which is crucial in various subjects. Problem-solving involves structured and systematic approaches, breaking complex issues into manageable parts and developing effective solutions. Practical application is incorporated into the curriculum, making the material more engaging and relatable. Group work and project-based learning are used daily to foster responsibility, teamwork, and communication skills. Language proficiency is generally high among German students, enhancing their understanding of various subjects and facilitating better communication with teachers and peers. The focus is also on foundational education, particularly in disciplines like science and math; it may result in improved academic achievement and higher marks. The German education system focuses on critical thinking, problem-solving, practical application, collaborative learning, language proficiency, and foundational solid education, which contribute to the overall success of students in the classroom.

According to Wang (2018), In China, students' academic performance is influenced by various learning styles, which may differ from those in other countries due to cultural and educational factors. Some notable learning styles include rote memorization, teacher-centred learning, group learning and competition, homework and self-study, cram schools and extracurricular tutoring. Rote memorization involves memorizing large amounts of information through repetition, which can help students achieve high test scores. Teacher-centred learning emphasizes respecting authority and maintaining discipline in the classroom. Group learning and competition motivate students to work harder and develop teamwork and collaboration skills. Homework and self-study encourage students to take responsibility for their learning and develop time management skills. Cram schools and extracurricular tutoring provide additional support and help students deepen their understanding of the subject matter. However, these learning styles may not be universally applicable. Educators should create an inclusive learning environment that caters to diverse learning preferences and incorporate more student-centred approaches, such as inquiry-based learning and project-based learning, to help students improve their academic performance in the classroom.

The VARK model, which categorizes learning styles into Visual, Auditory, Read/Write, and Kinesthetic, helps students in the United Arab Emirates (UAE) improve their academic performance. Visual learners prefer charts and diagrams to help them understand and retain information. Auditory learners benefit from discussions, group work, lectures, presentations, and written materials like textbooks and study guides. In the UAE, where English is taught as a second language, students benefit from written resources like notes and study guides. Kinesthetic learners who prefer hands-on activities, experiments, and physical movement benefit from interactive learning experiences. In the UAE, where many students come from culturally diverse backgrounds, kinesthetic learning can help them interact with the material and hone their critical thinking abilities. Teachers in the UAE often adopt a multi-sensory approach to cater to these diverse learning needs, ensuring that students receive the support they need to succeed in the classroom.

According to Veneracion (2018), understanding students' learning styles in the Philippines is crucial for improving their academic performance. Different learning styles include visual learners who prefer visual aids; auditory learners who prefer listening and discussing, kinesthetic learners who prefer hands-on experiences, logical-mathematical learners who enjoy reasoning and problem-solving, interpersonal learners who thrive in collaborative environments, and intrapersonal learners who prefer independent work. Teachers can use various teaching methods to cater to these different learning styles, creating a more inclusive and effective learning environment that benefits all students. Visual learners can benefit from colourful presentations, infographics, and demonstrations, auditory learners can benefit from group discussions, and kinesthetic learners can benefit from hands-on experiences. By incorporating these teaching methods, teachers can provide an atmosphere for learning that is more effective and inclusive and benefits all students,

ultimately leading to better academic performance.

In Pangasinan Division II, students have various learning styles that impact their academic performance. Understanding these styles can help better meet pupils' requirements; educators modify their teaching strategies. Visual learners prefer visual aids, while auditory learners benefit from listening and discussing. Kinesthetic learners prefer hands-on activities and practical experiences, and logical-mathematical learners thrive in environments involving critical thinking and logical analysis. Social engagement is the most effective way for interpersonal learners to learn and collaborate, benefiting from group projects and teamwork. Intrapersonal learners prefer independent learning, and teachers can provide more opportunities for independent study, self-assessment, and personalized learning goals. By understanding and accommodating these different learning styles, teachers may provide a more welcoming and productive learning atmosphere to enhance students' academic achievement and overall classroom success. By being aware of and sensitive to these various learning styles, Pangasinan Division II educators can create a more tolerant and productive learning atmosphere that accommodates the multiple demands of their pupils.

Understanding students' learning styles is essential for their academic performance in the San Manuel District. Learning styles are the distinctive ways people absorb, understand, and retain knowledge. Instructors can modify their pedagogical approaches to better accommodate these learning types, including kinesthetic, auditory, visual, and logical-mathematical. By catering to these understanding approaches, teachers may establish a more welcoming and productive learning atmosphere, resulting in higher academic performance and a better overall learning experience for all students.

In this study, the researcher aims to determine the learners' learning styles in San Manuel District, Pangasinan Division II, for SY 2023 – 2024.

Research Questions

This study determined the learning styles of primary learners in San Manuel District, Pangasinan Division II, for the school year 2023 – 2024. Specifically, this study answers the following questions:

1. What are the profile variables of respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1. age;
 - 1.2. sex;
 - 1.3. civil status;
 - 1.4. highest educational attainment;
 - 1.5. number of years in teaching; and
 - 1.6. number of relevant training and seminars attended?
2. What are the learning styles of primary learners?
3. Are there significant differences between the profile variables and their learning style?
4. Are there significant relationships between the profile variables and their learning style?
5. What development program can be proposed to enhance the learners' academic performance?

Methodology

Research Design

The researcher used a mixed research design or method. This research approach combines elements of both quantitative and qualitative research methods in a single study. This research design allows researchers to gather and analyze data from different perspectives, providing a more comprehensive understanding of the research topic. In a mixed research design, researchers typically collect and analyze quantitative data (such as numerical data, survey responses, or statistical information) and qualitative data (such as interviews, observations, or open-ended responses). By incorporating both types of data, researchers can gain a deeper insight into the research problem and triangulate findings to enhance the validity and reliability of the study. There are different ways to integrate quantitative and qualitative data in a mixed research design, including sequential designs (where one type of data collection and analysis follows the other), concurrent designs (where two kinds of data are collected and analyzed simultaneously), and transformative designs (where one type of data is used to inform the other). Overall, mixed research designs offer a more holistic research approach, allowing researchers to explore complex research questions, validate findings, and generate richer insights that may not be possible with just one research method.

Participants

This study's subjects are primary learners of public primary elementary schools and teachers in San Manuel District, Pangasinan Division II, for SY 2023 – 2024.

The population is separated into subgroups or strata according to specific traits that are significant to the study in this study, which is why stratified sampling is utilized. These characteristics include age, gender, income level, education level, or other relevant factors. After the population stratification, random samples are drawn from each stratum. More precise analysis and conclusions may be made by guaranteeing that every subgroup is sufficiently represented in the sample. When subgroups are of particular interest, or there are

known disparities within the population that might affect the study conclusions, stratified sampling is frequently employed to guarantee that the sample is representative of the whole population.

Table 1. *Distribution of Respondents N = 245*

<i>School Zone</i>	<i>Number of Learners</i>	<i>Number of Teachers</i>
1	57	19
2	51	18
3	66	24
4	36	16
5	35	14
Total	245	91

It helps reduce sampling errors, provides a more precise estimate of the population parameters, and allows for comparisons across different subgroups within the population.

Instruments

The researcher used a questionnaire checklist instrument made explicitly for the study based on the DepEd Order 31 S. 2012 and 2013, the Philippines' K-12 Basic Education Program implementation. The guidelines for implementing the K-12 Program in all public elementary and secondary schools in the Philippines are outlined in DepEd Order 31 S. 2012. The order provides an overview of the various parts of the program, such as the curriculum, instructional materials, teacher education, and evaluation. As described in the K-12 Policy, contextualized learning materials and activities must consider the diversity of learners' abilities, knowledge, learning styles, study habits, interests, motivation, multiple intelligences, and other circumstances.

The researchers also used interviews, one-on-one or group discussions with open-ended questions to gather in-depth insights. Focus groups: Group discussions with a few participants to explore their perspectives. Observations: Immersing oneself in the natural environment to observe and document behaviours. Content analysis: Analyzing text, images, or qualitative data.

To gather data using these tools, the researcher carefully designs their data collection methods, ensures validity and reliability, and analyses the data appropriately based on the research goals and questions..

Procedure

Before administering the research instrument, permission was secured from the Schools Division Superintendent of Pangasinan Division II, the District Supervisor, and the School Heads.

The researcher personally distributed and administered the questionnaires to all public primary school teachers and selected learners through stratified sampling in San Manuel District, Pangasinan Division II.

Likewise, the researcher personally retrieved the same questionnaires. To guarantee the highest level of impartiality in the replies, the researcher maintains the confidentiality of the data and responses.

The researchers also interviewed teachers and learners about their learning styles and the significance of their learning styles in their academic performance.

The researchers informed and oriented the respective public primary school teachers, learners, and school heads of the institutions regarding the purpose of the study.

Data Analysis

The following statistical instruments were employed to address the particular issues raised by the investigation.

The characteristics of the public primary school instructors, including age, sex, marital status, the highest level of education attained, number of years of teaching experience, and number of pertinent training and seminars attended, were ascertained using frequency counts and percentages. Frequent counts and percentages were used to determine the learners' learning styles.

To answer specific problem number 3, determining the differences between the profile variables and learners' learning styles, the analysis of variance (ANOVA) was utilized.

The Coded Pearson Product correlation coefficient was used to answer problem number 4, determining the relationship between the profile variables and the learners' learning styles.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the analysis's specifics and interpretations of the data about the study's problems.

Specifically, it presents the five (5) significant parts of the study through which the data gathered has been discussed. These include the profile variables of the respondents, the style of primary learners, the significant differences between profile variables and learners'

learning styles, and the significant relationship between profile variables and learners' learning styles.

Profile of the Respondents

Some variables related to the profile of the respondents in San Manuel District, Pangasinan Division II, are considered herein. Such variables included age, sex, civil status, highest educational attainment, number of years teaching and number of relevant training.

In this study, the public primary school teachers of San Manuel District, Pangasinan Division II, were taken as respondents. They were categorized according to certain variables.

Table 2 comprehensively shows the respondents' profiles. It provides information on various demographic variables, such as age, sex, civil status, highest educational qualification, number of years teaching, and number of trainings/seminars attended.

Table 2. Profile of the Respondents $N = 91$

Profile Variables	Variable Category	Frequency	Percentage	
Age	21 - 30	35	38%	
	31 - 40	27	30%	
	41 - 50	18	20%	
	51 - 60	9	10%	
	61 years and above	2	2%	
Sex	Male	12	13%	
	Female	79	87%	
Civil Status	Single	11	12%	
	Married	74	81%	
	Widow/Widower	6	7%	
	Separated	0	0%	
Highest Educational Qualification	Bachelor Degree Holder	16	18%	
	With M. A. Units	38	42%	
	M.A. Degree Holder	19	21%	
	With PhD/EdD Units	14	16%	
	PhD / EdD Degree Holder	4	3%	
Number of Years Teaching	5 years and below	11	12%	
	6 - 10	20	22%	
	11 - 15	27	30%	
	16 - 20	19	21%	
	21 years and above	14	15%	
Number of Trainings/Seminars	International	None	80	88%
		1 - 2	11	12%
		3 - 4	0	0%
		5 and above	0	0%
		National	None	67
	1 - 2		21	23%
	3 - 4		3	3%
	5 and above		0	0%
	Regional	None	22	24%
		1 - 2	38	42%
		3 - 4	20	22%
		5 and above	11	12%
	Division	None	10	11%
		1 - 2	22	24%
		3 - 4	28	31%
		5 and above	31	34%

Age. The results show that accounting for 38% of all participants, most respondents were between the ages of 21 and 30.

The second largest age group was 31 to 40, accounting for 30% of the respondents. The remaining age groups had a decreasing percentage of participation. The younger teachers (21-30 years old) are more likely to acknowledge the importance of learners' learning styles in their academic performance. This age group might be more open to exploring innovative teaching methods and adapting their instruction to cater to different learning styles. On the other hand, older teachers (51-60 years old) may have a smaller percentage of respondents, but this group could have more experience in the teaching field. They might have developed their teaching styles, including understanding and accommodating various learning styles.

Sex. This research result suggests that within the teaching profession, there is a higher percentage of females (87%) compared to males (13%). This disparity could be due to several factors. One possible reason is that women may be more inclined towards teaching due to their natural inclination towards nurturing and caring for others. Teaching allows them to shape young minds and contribute to society in a meaningful way. Another reason could be the societal expectations and gender roles that often influence career choices.

Historically, teaching and caregiving have been considered more suitable for women, leading to a higher representation of females in the teaching profession.

Additionally, the flexibility and work-life balance that teaching often provides can be more appealing to women who may have family responsibilities or wish to balance their personal and professional lives. Lastly, the accessibility and affordability of education for women may have contributed to this trend. As more women access education, they are better equipped to pursue careers in teaching and other related fields. The higher percentage of females in the teaching profession could be attributed to personal inclinations, societal expectations, work-life balance, and access to education.

Civil Status. This research result indicates that in this particular study, most respondents were married, followed by single individuals, and then widows or widowers. Interestingly, there were no separated participants. The reason for the higher number of married individuals could be various factors. One possible explanation is that marriage is a more stable and long-lasting relationship, and people who have been married longer might be more likely to participate in studies.

Additionally, married individuals might have a stronger sense of community and social support, which could encourage them to engage in research activities. Another factor could be the age distribution of the participants. Married people might be older on average, as they have had more time to get married, stay married, and potentially lose their spouse through widowhood. Older individuals may be more inclined to participate in research as they have more life experiences to share. Furthermore, the study's topic or purpose attracted more married individuals, as their experiences and perspectives could be more relevant to the research question. It is also essential to consider any potential sampling bias, which could have led to a higher representation of married individuals in the study. Lastly, the low number of separated respondents and the absence of separated individuals might be due to the study's specific context or the participants' circumstances. Separated individuals might have been less interested in participating, or the study's criteria might have excluded them.

Highest Educational Qualification. The table provided presents information about the highest educational qualifications of teachers in a particular context. It shows the distribution of teachers based on their academic qualifications, which can help understand the academic background of the teaching workforce. Most teachers in the survey are Bachelor's Degree Holders, comprising 18% of the total respondents. The remaining 42% are M.A. Unit holders, containing 42%. These teachers may pursue a Master of Arts degree or have completed some units or courses towards a Master's degree. The remaining 21% are M.A. Degree Holders, with 19 teachers demonstrating a higher level of education. The remaining 16% are PhD/EdD Unitholders, with 14 teachers pursuing a Doctoral degree or completing some units or courses towards a Doctoral program. The final category has the least number of teachers, with only four completing their Doctoral studies. The table highlights that most teachers in this context have a Master's degree or are pursuing higher education. This suggests a commitment to professional development and a desire to enhance their teaching skills and knowledge. However, it is also important to note that there is still a portion of teachers with only a Bachelor's degree, which could be an area for improvement in promoting further education among educators.

Number of Years Teaching. The information presented presents a distribution of the number of years of teaching for a group of teachers. The data is divided into four categories based on the years of teaching experience. The list of teachers in this category includes those with five years or less experience, those with 6 to 10 years of experience, those with 11 to 15 years of experience, those with 16 to 20 years of experience, and those with 21 years or more. This data can help understand the distribution of teaching experience among teachers and identify trends or areas of focus for professional development. For instance, it shows that a significant portion (30%) of the teachers have 11 to 15 years of experience, which could indicate a stable workforce in this age range. However, there is also a considerable number of teachers (22%) with 6 to 10 years of experience, which might suggest the need for retention strategies to keep these teachers engaged and motivated.

Several Relevant Training/Seminars Attended. The table presents data on the number of training/seminar attendances by teachers, categorized by the level of participation (None, 1-2, 3-4, and 5 and above) and the geographical scope (International, National, Regional, and Division). Most teachers (88%) did not attend international training/seminars, while only 12% attended 1-2. There were no reported cases of teachers attending 3-4 or 5 and above training/seminars. In the National category, 74% attended no national training/seminars, while 23% attended 1-2. Regionally, 24% attended no regional training/seminars, while 42% attended 1-2. In the Division category, 11% attended no division training/seminars, with 24% attending 1-2 training/seminars. The data suggests that most teachers in these categories have attended few training/seminars, either nationally, regionally, or internationally. However, there is a considerable variation in the participation rates depending on the geographical scope and the specific category. The Division category shows a higher percentage of teachers attending more training/seminars, particularly in the 3-4 category. This information can be helpful for educational institutions and policymakers to understand the professional development needs and opportunities of teachers in different regions and scopes.

Overall, Table 2 provides a detailed overview of the respondents' demographic characteristics, offering valuable insights for further analysis and discussion in the research context.

Learning Style of Primary Learners

The primary purpose of this study was to determine the learning style of primary learners in San Manuel District, Pangasinan Division

II, for SY 2023 – 2024.

Table 3 presents the learning styles of primary learners in San Manuel District, Pangasinan Division II, for SY 2023 – 2024.

A learner's learning style refers to the unique and individualized ways a person processes, perceives, interacts with, and retains information when engaged in learning activities. It is the preferred method or approach that a learner uses to make sense of new information and concepts, and it plays a significant role in determining the effectiveness of their learning experiences. Several theories and models attempt to categorize and understand learning styles, with the most popular being the VARK model and Kolb's Experiential Learning Theory. Understanding a learner's preferred learning style can help better meet their pupils' requirements; teachers modify their pedagogical approaches.

By incorporating various learning styles into their teaching techniques, teachers may establish a more welcoming and productive learning environment, ultimately enhancing the overall learning experience for their students.

The table below shows the learning style preferences of primary learners across five different zones. Physical (Kinesthetic) Learning: This learning style involves using one's body and hands. It is preferred by 14% of the total learners, with the highest number in Zone 3. Visual (Spatial) Learning: Visual learners prefer using images and spatial understanding. This is the most common learning style among primary learners, with 56% preferring this style. The highest number of visual learners is in Zone 1. Auditory Learning: Auditory learners prefer using sound and music for learning. 22% of the learners prefer this style, with the highest number in Zone 3. Verbal (Read/Write) Learning: Learners prefer this style to reading and writing for learning. It is the choice of 5% of the learners, with the highest number in Zone 5. Logical (Mathematical) Learning: These learners prefer logic, reasoning, and systems. 3% of the learners prefer this style, with the highest number in Zone 3.

Most primary learners prefer visual (spatial) learning, followed by auditory learning. Educators must recognize and accommodate these varied learning styles to support optimal learning experiences for all students.

Table 3. *Learning Style of Primary Learners Along Physical (Kinesthetic) Learning Style*

	Zone 1 Number of Learners	Zone 2 Number of Learners	Zone 3 Number of Learners	Zone 4 Number of Learners	Zone 5 Number of Learners	Total Number of Learners	%
Physical (Kinesthetic) Learning	5	7	9	8	6	35	14%
Visual (Spatial) Learning	35	31	37	19	16	138	56%
Auditory Learning	14	10	15	7	8	54	22%
Verbal (Read/Write) Learning	2	3	2	1	4	12	5%
Logical (Mathematical) Learning	1	0	3	1	1	6	3%
Total	57	51	66	36	35	245	100%

Physical (Kinesthetic) Learning Style

Table 3 shows the learning style preferences of primary learners across five different zones. Physical (Kinesthetic) Learning: this learning style involves using one's body and hands. It is preferred by 14% of the total learners, with the highest number in Zone 3.

The teacher's respondents said that every learner is unique and may have a preferred learning style or a combination of styles. Some common learning styles include visual (learning through seeing), auditory (learning through hearing), kinesthetic (learning through doing), logical (mathematical) learning style and read/write (learning through reading and writing) learning style. Educators must recognize and cater to different learning styles to support their students' diverse needs. The teachers employ multiple teaching strategies and techniques to meet the needs of various learners. They gave some examples for visual learners. To assist them grasp topics, they use charts, diagrams, and other visual aids. For auditory learners, they incorporate discussions, lectures, and audio recordings into the lesson. For kinesthetic learners, they provide hands-on activities, interactive simulations, and opportunities for movement. For read/write learners, they offer written materials and textbooks and encourage note-taking. They also said that accommodating different learning styles can enhance the learning experience for students; academic performance is influenced by various factors beyond just learning styles. Motivation, engagement, study habits, and support systems also significantly influence academic success.

The Kinesthetic learners said that being a kinesthetic learner can enhance academic performance for some individuals, allowing for a more hands-on and experiential approach to learning. This can lead to better retention of information, improved understanding of concepts, and increased engagement with the material. Being a kinesthetic learner helps me process and respond to information more interactively and dynamically, which can ultimately benefit our interactions and the assistance I get from the teacher.

Kinesthetic learners prefer hands-on learning opportunities, such as demonstrations, simulations, and videos of "real" things, as well as case studies, practice, and applications. They value their own experiences more than others. This learning style enhances academic performance by allowing students to apply knowledge in real-life situations, improving understanding and retention. However, they may need help with traditional lecture-based teaching methods. Kinesthetic learners excel in hands-on experiences and activities

involving movement, touch, and experimentation. Traditional desks are replaced in the classroom with standing desks, which may cause distractions for Kinesthetic learners. Students who prefer this learning style may find engaging in hands-on activities, such as case studies or working examples, easier than relying on lectures.

Clayton (2020) said that kinesthetic learning, which involves physical movement and hands-on experiences, can significantly improve academic performance in the classroom. This approach caters to students' diverse learning needs and encourages active engagement with the material. By incorporating kinesthetic activities, educators can make learning more enjoyable, memorable, and easier to understand for students with this preference. Research shows that students who learn through kinesthetic methods tend to retain and understand the subject matter better. Various forms of kinesthetic activities in the classroom include experiments, role-playing, movement and physical exercises, field trips, and group work. These activities stimulate thinking and creativity and provide real-life experiences that reinforce learning. In conclusion, incorporating kinesthetic learning styles in the classroom can significantly enhance academic performance by catering to student's diverse needs and creating an engaging and effective learning environment.

According to Herrity (2022), every individual has a learning method that works best for them. Depending on your preferences and skills, there are several learning styles that you may connect to. Some people learn best by hearing about a subject; others require hands-on experience. Understanding the various learning styles allows you to adapt your communication methods to the audience's demands.

This article lists eight common learning styles and strategies to engage with these different types of learners. Kinesthetic learning, or "learning through movement," is a method that enhances academic performance by providing hands-on, experiential, and interactive experiences. This approach helps students understand and retain information by engaging their senses and bodies. Benefits include higher memory and retention, heightened motivation and engagement, sharper critical thinking and problem-solving abilities, a better comprehension of abstract ideas, and a promotion of cooperation and teamwork. However, it's important to note that not all students benefit equally from kinesthetic learning, and a well-rounded and inclusive approach to teaching is crucial for maximizing academic performance. Therefore, incorporating various learning styles is essential for a successful learning experience.

Visual (Spatial) Learning Style

Table 4 also shows the result of Visual (Spatial) Learning. Visual learners prefer using images and spatial understanding for learning. This is the most common learning style among primary learners, with 56% preferring this style. The highest number of visual learners is in Zone 1.

Table 4. *Learning Style of Primary Learners Along Visual (Spatial) Learning Style*

	Zone 1 Number of Learners	Zone 2 Number of Learners	Zone 3 Number of Learners	Zone 4 Number of Learners	Zone 5 Number of Learners	Total Number of Learners	%
Physical (Kinesthetic) Learning	5	7	9	8	6	35	14%
Visual (Spatial) Learning	35	31	37	19	16	138	56%
Auditory Learning	14	10	15	7	8	54	22%
Verbal (Read/Write) Learning	2	3	2	1	4	12	5%
Logical (Mathematical) Learning	1	0	3	1	1	6	3%
Total	57	51	66	36	35	245	100%

Primary instructors need to understand that pupils have a variety of learning preferences, including kinesthetic, auditory, and visual learners. By understanding your students' diverse needs, we can tailor our teaching methods to accommodate these various styles. This involves incorporating visual aids, hands-on activities, group discussions, and other interactive techniques in our lessons.

By accommodating diverse learning styles, Teachers may establish a more welcoming and stimulating classroom that may enhance pupils' understanding and memory of the material. While it may not guarantee better academic performance for every student, addressing diverse learning styles can help create a more effective and supportive educational experience for our learners.

The learners said they are visual learners because they typically prefer to process information through pictures, diagrams, graphs, and other visual aids. This learning style can benefit academic performance as it can help us better understand and retain information by seeing it visually represented. They also said that visual learning improves their comprehension, memory retention, and the ability to recall information when needed. Incorporating visual techniques such as colour coding, mind maps, and charts into studying as visual learners enhances our learning experience and academic performance.

Visual learning styles using images, diagrams, and videos can significantly impact academic performance. These students understand complex concepts better by relating them to visual representations. They learn more effectively through graphical formats like flowcharts, infographics, or demonstrations. Understanding the impact of visual learning styles on academic performance can help educators tailor teaching methods to accommodate these students' preferences, ultimately enhancing their learning experience and

overall educational success. Sketchnotes, a combination of doodling and text, can be beneficial for visual learners, as they enable quicker processing of information and attach more meaning to the content. This mode, also known as Graphic (G), includes designs, white space, patterns, shapes, and various formats used to highlight and convey information. For those with a visual preference, diagrams with meaningful symbols and connections are helpful, while those with a Read/Write preference may prefer more words in boxes.

Pineda (2019) said that from the three learning style preferences, only visual learning style preference significantly affected pupils' academic performance, especially in Filipino. Nevertheless, all three learning style preferences only partially affect pupils' academic performance in the rest of the core subjects (English, Mathematics, and Science). In this view, teachers are encouraged to put some ingredients in delivering their pedagogical instructions further according to what would best fit their pupils' learning style preferences.

According to Mina (2019), visual learners are the students who need to see the teachers' body language and facial expressions. On the other hand, Haptic learners learn fast by using their sense of touch literally, such as drawing and model building. Kinesthetic learners are students who enjoy working with their hands or the entire body movement. The learners can be given activities to be physically active. Examples are dancing, role modelling, and other moving activities. If the teacher can provide activities through their learning styles, math and other subjects will attain increased achievement.

According to Yazici (2016), learning styles affect learning and academic achievement. Students saw tactile, auditory, and individual learning modes as small preferences, while they valued visual, group, and kinesthetic learning modes as primary preferences, according to Magulod Jr. (2019). This data is derived from examining students' study habits, preferred learning styles, and academic accomplishment levels. Additionally, he asserts that students' academic success is strongly correlated with their study habits, learning preferences, and routines. As a primary teacher, it is crucial to acknowledge that students have a variety of learning styles, including kinesthetic, auditory, and visual learners.

Auditory Learning Style

Table 5 also shows that 22% of the learners' respondents prefer this auditory learning style, with the highest number in Zone 3. Auditory learners prefer using sound and music for learning.

The Teachers said that many learners prefer the auditory learning style because it allows them to process information by listening and hearing. This learning style is effective for learners who learn better through verbal communication, such as listening to lectures, discussions, and explanations. Auditory learners often retain information better when listening to it rather than reading or seeing it visually. Additionally, auditory learners excel in speaking, listening, and oral communication tasks.

According to the learners, they prefer the auditory learning style for several reasons.

I enjoy learning through listening more than other methods, such as reading or doing hands-on activities. Hearing information aloud helps some students remember and recall it more quickly than reading or seeing it in written form. Auditory learners may be better at processing and understanding information when presented verbally, as opposed to visually or kinesthetically. Listening to lectures, discussions, music, podcasts, or other auditory materials can be more engaging and enjoyable for some students than other learning methods. Some students said they find it easier to focus and concentrate in an auditory-based learning environment, where they can listen to explanations and instructions.

Table 5. Learning Style of Primary Learners Along Auditory Learning Style

	Zone 1	Zone 2	Zone 3	Zone 4	Zone 5	Total	%
	Number of Learners	Number of Learners	Number of Learners	Number of Learners	Number of Learners	Number of Learners	
Physical (Kinesthetic) Learning	5	7	9	8	6	35	14%
Visual (Spatial) Learning	35	31	37	19	16	138	56%
Auditory Learning	14	10	15	7	8	54	22%
Verbal (Read/Write) Learning	2	3	2	1	4	12	5%
Logical (Mathematical) Learning	1	0	3	1	1	6	3%
Total	57	51	66	36	35	245	100%

Auditory learners are skilled listeners who focus on the tone and rate of speech, often benefiting from supplemental resources like videos or audio components. They benefit from group discussions, reading aloud, and repeating content. Strategies to help auditory learners include using Flipgrid for question posting, Synth for podcasting, and "telephone" activities where students retell a story in their own words. Aural learners prefer heard or spoken information, learning best from lectures, group discussions, radio, email, mobile phones, and speaking. They sort things out by saying first rather than sorting out ideas and then talking. Auditory learners excel in listening and discussing information, preferring lectures, group discussions, and verbal explanations. They often excel in oral presentations and group discussions. Recording lectures or discussions for later review and using techniques like repeating information,

creating mnemonics, or using rhymes can help retain concepts.

According to Cruz (2024), auditory learning is one of the most popular modalities. When applying their knowledge in practical settings, auditory learners are often more pragmatic than their non-audible counterparts. For auditory learners, listening, comprehending, and applying knowledge are essential. Even though auditory learners can struggle to organize several bits of knowledge at once, with the proper guidance, these thinkers will succeed in life. Auditory learning benefits children by promoting social development, building vocabulary and communication skills, and fostering critical thinking. It encourages interaction, idea-sharing, and problem-solving, which are crucial in school and life. It also promotes problem-solving abilities.

Mead (2022) said that auditory learners learn best through their sense of hearing, remembering and understanding new concepts better when explained out loud. They enjoy music and follow spoken directions. Auditory learners prefer reading out loud, preferring someone to read to them. Their understanding is more vital when teachers explain concepts to them rather than when given reading assignments.

According to Fleming (2020), auditory learners are good listeners and social, often distracted by classroom distractions. They learn through voice recordings and vocabulary word invents.

Verbal (Read/Write) Learning Style

Table 6 also shows how many learners prefer the verbal (read/write) learning style. This style likes to read and write for learning. Five percent of the learners chose this style, with the highest number in Zone 5.

According to the instructor responders, students favour verbal learning approaches because they perceive spoken language as a more understandable and memorable way to communicate knowledge. Activities like reading aloud, participating in conversations, and listening to lectures are often areas where verbal learners shine. Thanks to this learning style, they may process information more efficiently through auditory channels, which also helps them retain and apply what they have learned.

The learners have several reasons why they prefer to be verbal learners. They find it easier to understand and remember information when presented through language, as they are comfortable with words. Some learners have strong language skills, making verbal learning a natural fit. They enjoy discussion and social settings, preferring traditional teaching methods. Verbal learners may also find the accessibility of resources like audiobooks, podcasts, online lectures, and language learning apps more engaging and accessible than other learning materials. Learners favouring a more conventional approach to education tend to favour verbal learning.

Table 6. *Learning Style of Primary Learners Along Verbal (Read/Write) Learning Style*

	Zone 1 Number of Learners	Zone 2 Number of Learners	Zone 3 Number of Learners	Zone 4 Number of Learners	Zone 5 Number of Learners	Total Number of Learners	%
Physical (Kinesthetic) Learning	5	7	9	8	6	35	14%
Visual (Spatial) Learning	35	31	37	19	16	138	56%
Auditory Learning	14	10	15	7	8	54	22%
Verbal (Read/Write) Learning	2	3	2	1	4	12	5%
Logical (Mathematical) Learning	1	0	3	1	1	6	3%
Total	57	51	66	36	35	245	100%

Read/write (Linguistic) learners prefer written text and often create diagrams, lists, or hierarchies to organize information. They can benefit from using tools like Storyboard or PowerPoint to create presentations. Learners and teachers highly seek this preference, as it emphasizes text-based input and output, particularly in manuals, reports, essays, and assignments. People with this preference are often addicted to PowerPoint, the Internet, lists, diaries, dictionaries, thesauri, quotations, and words. PowerPoint presentations and information on sites like Wikipedia are suited to this preference, as there is rarely an auditory channel or presentation that uses visual symbols. Linguistic learners excel in reading and writing, note-taking, summarising, and discussing written material. This learning style enhances their reading and writing skills, improving their academic performance.

According to Cabual (2019), most learners in his study prefer a read-and-write and visual learning style. He said these pupils learn best by doing things by hand since they are hands-on learners. This model identifies students' learning styles, and allowing students to access the information they are comfortable with will increase their academic confidence. The teacher gains a better perspective on implementing these learning styles into lesson plans and study techniques.

According to Operiano (2022), linguistic learning style is an individual's preference for language-based learning, such as reading, writing, and discussing. Howard Gardner's multiple intelligence theory suggests this style can contribute to higher academic performance in literature, languages, history, and social sciences. However, it may be less effective in subjects like mathematics or sciences, where language is not the primary mode of understanding. To grasp the material better, students may need to develop other learning strategies, such as visual or kinesthetic approaches. The effectiveness of a linguistic learning style depends on the subject and the individual's ability to adapt and utilize other strategies. A well-rounded educational approach can cater to diverse student needs.

Chan (2021) said that linguistic learning style refers to an individual's preference for language processing and acquiring information. It can enhance engagement and understanding of the material, but its effectiveness depends on the subject, student, and instruction quality. In subjects requiring language, such as literature, language arts, or foreign languages, linguistic learning styles can be effective through group discussions, debates, and presentations. However, incorporating various teaching methods can improve academic performance in subjects like mathematics or science, where visual and practical strategies are more beneficial. A well-rounded and inclusive approach to teaching, accommodating diverse learning styles, can lead to higher academic performance.

Logical (Mathematical) Learning Style

Table 7 shows the results of the learners who preferred the logical (Mathematical) learning style: 3% of the respondents, with the highest number in Zone 3.

According to the teachers, logical learners excel in academic settings that allow them to analyze patterns, numbers, and relationships. To improve their academic performance, we should, as teachers, provide structured, organized information, use visual aids like diagrams and charts, encourage problem-solving activities, offer independent study opportunities, and provide collaboration opportunities. These strategies cater to their learning style and help them understand complex concepts.

Table 7. *Learning Style of Primary Learners Along Logical (Mathematical) Learning Style*

	Zone 1 Number of Learners	Zone 2 Number of Learners	Zone 3 Number of Learners	Zone 4 Number of Learners	Zone 5 Number of Learners	Total Number of Learners	%
Physical (Kinesthetic) Learning	5	7	9	8	6	35	14%
Visual (Spatial) Learning	35	31	37	19	16	138	56%
Auditory Learning	14	10	15	7	8	54	22%
Verbal (Read/Write) Learning	2	3	2	1	4	12	5%
Logical (Mathematical) Learning	1	0	3	1	1	6	3%
Total	57	51	66	36	35	245	100%

Logical learners prefer clear, logical presentations, so as teachers, we should ensure their lessons are well-organized and presented in a logical sequence. They can also engage in hands-on activities that require critical thinking and problem-solving skills. Additionally, they can explore topics of interest in more depth through independent research projects. By incorporating group activities and discussions, teachers can effectively address the learning needs of logical learners and improve their academic performance.

According to logical (mathematical) learners prefer a rational approach to learning mathematics because they enjoy working with numbers and symbols, are satisfied with logical reasoning, prefer structured learning, excel in analytical thinking, and are interested in fields that require mathematical skills.

They also prefer logical learners because their structured and organized approach makes it easier for them to understand complex concepts. They feel more confident in their understanding and can excel in subjects requiring critical thinking and problem-solving skills, which encourages analytical reasoning and systematic decision-making.

A mathematical or logical learning style is a student's preference for learning and processing information using analytical, rational, and numerical methods. These students think structured and systematically, often focusing on patterns, sequences, and cause-and-effect relationships. This learning style is particularly relevant in mathematics, science, and computer programming. The impact of a mathematical or logical learning style on academic performance might vary based on the situation and be either a positive or lousy subject and the teaching methods employed. There are some key points to consider. Students with a mathematical or logical learning style often excel in subjects that require analytical thinking, problem-solving, and logical reasoning. They are usually adept at understanding complex concepts and breaking them into smaller, manageable parts. This can improve mathematics, physics, computer science, and engineering performance.

However, students with a solid mathematical or logical learning style may need help in subjects that rely heavily on verbal, creative, or interpersonal skills, such as literature, history, or social sciences. They might need help to grasp abstract concepts or express their thoughts and ideas in these areas. Educators should incorporate teaching methods that cater to their preferences to optimize students' academic performance with a mathematical or logical learning style. This may include using visual aids, diagrams, charts, and step-by-step explanations to present information. Providing hands-on learning and experimentation opportunities can also help engage these students and improve their understanding of the material. While a mathematical or logical learning style can be advantageous, fostering a balance of skills in students is essential. Encouraging them to develop and utilize other learning styles, such as visual, auditory, or kinesthetic, can help them become more versatile and practical across various subjects. Mathematical or logical learning styles can significantly impact a student's academic performance positively and negatively. Understanding this learning style and adapting teaching methods can help students excel in subjects that align with their strengths while encouraging the development of a diverse range of learning skills.

According to Brown (2022), logical learning styles can be quite effective in enhancing academic performance in the classroom, particularly for students with a natural affinity for rational thinking and analytical approaches. This learning style focuses on organizing information in a structured, systematic manner, using reasoning and problem-solving skills. Students who prefer a logical learning style frequently do well in disciplines like science, math, and technology, where the material is more structured and relies on a step-by-step approach. They tend to perform better on tasks that require critical thinking, analysis, and deductive reasoning. However, it is essential to note that different students have varying learning styles, and what works well for a logical learner might be less effective for someone with a more visual, auditory, or kinesthetic learning style. A diverse and inclusive teaching approach that caters to multiple learning styles can lead to better overall academic performance in the classroom. A logical learning style can effectively enhance academic performance for students gravitating toward this approach. However, it is crucial to recognize and accommodate different learning styles to ensure the best possible outcomes for all students.

According to Logsdon (2022), students with logical-mathematical learning styles thrive when taught using visual materials, computers, statistical and analytical programs, and hands-on projects. Students prefer organized, goal-oriented activities that require mathematical reasoning and logic to unstructured, creative activities with ambiguous learning objectives.

Bohringer (2021) said that a logical learning style, characterized by analytical and systematic learning, can significantly improve academic performance in mathematics, science, and technology. This approach fosters critical thinking, problem-solving, and breaking down complex ideas into manageable parts, enhancing understanding and retention. However, not all students excel solely through a logical learning style. Combining different learning styles, such as visual, auditory, and kinesthetic, can provide a more comprehensive understanding of the subject matter. In conclusion, while a logical learning style can enhance academic performance, it's essential to recognize and incorporate other learning styles to cater to diverse student needs.

Table 8 summarizes primary learners' learning styles based on the total number of learners surveyed. Here is a breakdown of the results: Physical (Kinesthetic) Learning: 35 learners, accounting for 14% of the total, prefer learning through physical activities and hands-on experiences. These learners benefit from movement and tactile experiences to understand and retain information.

Visual (Spatial) Learning: Most learners, 138 in total, representing 56% of the sample, prefer visual learning styles. These learners excel in understanding information through visual aids, such as charts, diagrams, and images.

Auditory Learning: 54 learners, making up 22% of the total, prefer auditory learning styles. These learners learn best through listening to lectures, discussions, and audio materials.

Verbal (Read/Write) Learning: 12 learners, accounting for 5% of the total, prefer learning through reading and writing. These learners excel in written communication and benefit from reading and writing activities.

Logical (Mathematical) Learning: 6 learners prefer logical and mathematical learning styles, representing 3% of the total. These learners excel in problem-solving, critical thinking, and reasoning activities.

Most primary learners in the sample prefer visual (spatial) learning styles, followed by auditory learning. Understanding the distribution of learning styles can help educators tailor their teaching methods to accommodate students' diverse preferences and enhance their learning experiences.

Table 8. Summary of Learning Style of Primary Learners

	<i>Total Number of Learners</i>	<i>%</i>
Physical (Kinesthetic) Learning	35	14%
Visual (Spatial) Learning	138	56%
Auditory Learning	54	22%
Verbal (Read/Write) Learning	12	5%
Logical (Mathematical) Learning	6	3%
Total	245	100%

The high percentage of respondents preferring the visual (spatial) learning style could be attributed to several factors. Visual learning is often considered a more engaging and stimulating way to absorb information, as it involves the use of images, diagrams, and visual aids that can help learners better understand and remember concepts. Additionally, visual learners may find it easier to process and interpret information when it is presented in a visual format, making learning more accessible and enjoyable for them.

On the other hand, the lower percentage of respondents preferring the logical (mathematical) learning style may be due to the nature of this learning style. Logical learners excel in problem-solving, critical thinking, and reasoning activities, which may not be as appealing or readily accessible to all learners. Some students may find logical and mathematical tasks challenging or less engaging compared to other learning styles that offer more hands-on or visual learning experiences. Individual preferences, learning environments, teaching methods, and personal experiences shape a student's preferred learning style. Educators must recognize and accommodate students' diverse learning preferences to create inclusive and compelling learning experiences.

Sarican (2021) said that learning styles, including linguistic, logical, auditory, visual, and kinesthetic, significantly influence students' academic performance. Linguistic learners excel in language-based subjects, while logical learners thrive in reasoning and problem-

solving. Auditory learners benefit from active listening and class discussions, while visual learners process information through images and diagrams. Kinesthetic learners prefer hands-on, experiential learning, and teachers can support them by incorporating more practical activities. Recognizing and accommodating different learning styles can positively impact students' academic performance. Teachers should create a diverse and inclusive classroom setting that meets the needs of all students, regardless of their preferred learning style. By incorporating these styles into their teaching methods, educators can better support students' learning and improve their academic outcomes. This approach will ultimately lead to better educational outcomes for all students.

Aboe (2019) states that every student has different learning styles. They have their way of studying something that makes them comfortable and allows them to absorb and understand the material quickly. He also highlights that although some students find reading a book more accessible and learning the content by heart, others need notes to understand the subject. Some students would rather watch a video instruction than read a manual when learning a new skill.

According to Ramirez (2022), learning styles significantly affect academic performance. This suggests that learning style and educational success are substantially correlated, implying that pupils' learning preferences and academic success are related. Knowing this, educators may design classes and activities that best fit their students' learning preferences. In doing so, they say their students enhance their abilities and improve their academic achievement.

The preferences of students' learning styles are crucial to understanding and improving their comprehension level and understanding how they learn. Teachers need to identify and comprehend students' preferred learning styles to employ effective teaching techniques that correspond to the various learning preferences of the students. The alignment between students' learning styles and teachers' teaching styles leads to better comprehension and understanding of complex lessons. The teaching-learning process can benefit significantly from students' and teachers' awareness of different learning styles (Yasmin, Akbar, & Hussain, 2016).

Differences Between the Learning Style of Primary Learners and the Respondents Across their Profile Variables

This section presents the differences between primary learners' learning styles and the respondents' profile variables in San Manuel District, Pangasinan Division II, for the SY 2023 – 2024.

The table summarises the computed ANOVA as indicated by the F-value for each area covered with its corresponding significance level. This was done to make a more in-depth analysis of the data generated in this study, whereby the profiles of the public primary school teacher respondents in San Manuel District, Pangasinan Division II, were compared in their level of impact of learners' learning style on their academic performance.

The individual computation of the ANOVA for each of the different indicators covered in this study is visual (spatial) learning style, auditory learning style, Kinesthetic (Tactile) learning style, reading/writing (linguistic) learning style, and Logical/ Mathematical learning style.

Table 9 presents the ANOVA showing the significant differences in the learners' learning style and academic performance of the respondents across their profile variables.

Table 9 presents the mean differences perceived by the respondents in the learners' learning style on their academic performance across their profile variables. The variables include visual (spatial) learning style, auditory learning style, kinesthetic (tactile) learning style, reading/writing (linguistic) learning style, and logical/mathematical learning style. The results are presented as F-values (F) and significance levels (Sig.).

Table 9. Mean Differences Between the Learning Style of Primary Learners Across the Profile Variables Respondents

	<i>Visual (spatial) learning style</i>		<i>Auditory Learning Style,</i>		<i>Kinesthetic (Tactile) Learning Style</i>		<i>Reading/Writing (Linguistic) Learning Style</i>		<i>Logical/ Mathematical Learning Style</i>	
	<i>F</i>	<i>Sig.</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Sig.</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Sig.</i>	<i>Sig.</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Sig.</i>
Age	1.065	.331	.267	.265	.722	.058	.638	.725	.070	.637
Sex	.834	.368	.163	.147	.574	.287	.429	.579	.287	.429
Civil Status	.368	.279	.847	.853	.226	.365	.308	.223	.380	.315
Highest Educational Attainment	.532	.328	.536	.544	.253	.854	.532	.252	.856	.536
Length of Service as a Teacher	.541	.339	.680	.665	.388	.287	.212	.389	.287	.225
Relevant Trainings/Seminars										
International	.276	.129	.728	.726	.076	.268	.138	.076	.268	.151
National	.763	.257	.209	.208	.131	.242	.174	.134	.245	.172
Regional	.345	.243	.637	.635	.352	.443	.251	.356	.439	.256
Division	.282	.079	.474	.473	.275	.361	.323	.283	.348	.329

The study found that respondents do not perceive a significant difference in the impact of visual, auditory, kinesthetic, reading/writing, and logical/mathematical learning styles on academic performance. The mean difference in the impact of visual learning style is 1.065, auditory is .834, kinesthetic is .267, reading/writing is .058, and logical/mathematical is .070. According to the respondents, there was no discernible change in the impact of visual, auditory, kinesthetic, reading/writing, or logical/mathematical learning styles on learners' academic performance. The results suggest that the different learning styles affect academic performance insignificantly.

The study found no significant difference in the learning styles on academic performance across age, gender, civil status, highest educational attainment, length of service as a teacher, or relevant training/seminars. This suggests that the learning styles on academic performance do not significantly vary based on age, gender, civil status, marital status, highest educational attainment, length of service as a teacher, or the type of professional development teachers attend. The respondents also did not perceive a significant difference in learning styles on academic performance based on the kind of training and seminars attended. The findings suggest that the learning styles on academic performance do not significantly vary based on age, gender, civil status, highest educational attainment, or relevant training/seminars.

The participants don't think there are any notable variations in learning styles and academic performance across various profile variables such as age, sex, civil status, highest educational attainment, length of service as a teacher, and relevant training/seminars.

Relationship Between the Learners' Learning Style and the Respondents' Profile Variables

The relationships between the learners' learning styles and the respondents analyze file variables must be considered to further analyze the data gathered in this study. This was done using the Pearson coefficient of correlation (Pearson r) and the t-test for significant correlation. Table 10 shows such relationships.

Table 10 presents the results of a research study investigating the relationship between the learners' learning styles, academic performance, and various profile variables. The profile variables include Age, Sex, Civil Status, Highest Educational Attainment, Length of Service teaching, Related Training/Seminars, Division, Regional, and National. The table focuses on the correlation between these factors and the significance of the relationship. The study used Pearson correlation to analyze the data and determined the significance level at 0.05.

The study found a moderate positive correlation between age and the learning styles of primary learners on academic performance. As the age of respondents increased, so did their perception of the importance of learning styles in affecting students' academic performance. However, there was a weak negative correlation between sex and learning styles on academic performance. Civil status also showed a moderate positive correlation, suggesting that civil status may influence learning styles. The highest educational attainment had a mild positive correlation with the learning styles on academic performance. The length of service teaching also had a weak positive correlation, suggesting that longer teaching durations resulted in a more excellent perception of learning styles influencing students' academic performance. The division of respondents had a moderate positive correlation with the perceived impact of learning styles on academic performance.

Table 10. Relationship Between the Learners' Learning Style and Respondents the Profile Variables

Profile Variables	Pearson Correlation	Sig. (2-tailed)
Age	.486**	.853
Sex	-.081	.223
Civil Status	.392	.492
Highest Educational Attainment	.387**	.032
Length of Service teaching	.287	.084
Related Training/Seminars		
Division	.452**	.043
Regional	.288	.286
National	.572	.185
International	.453	.337

The Pearson correlation coefficient for the division was .452, indicating a moderate positive relationship between the learners' learning styles and the division they belong to. Regional and national variables had weak positive relationships with the learning styles on academic performance.

Understanding these learning styles can contribute to better academic performance for national students. International variables had a weak positive relationship with the learning styles on academic performance but were not significant enough to conclude any significant impact on academic performance.

The research results in Table 10 show that the division and national variables have a significant relationship with the learners' learning styles on their academic performance.

Understanding and catering to learning styles might be more crucial for students in certain divisions and national backgrounds, which could lead to better academic performance. However, the regional and international variables must show a significant solid relationship

between learning styles and academic performance.

Conclusion

Based on the findings above of this study, the following conclusions were formulated:

The study reveals that most female teachers aged 21-30 are married and have Bachelor's degrees, M.A., and PhD/EdD degrees. They participate in various trainings and seminars, providing insights into professional development and future educational policies.

The research indicates that most primary learners prefer visual learning, primarily due to the engaging nature of visual aids like images, diagrams, and videos. This makes learning more accessible and enjoyable for learners. Conversely, a smaller percentage prefer logical learning involving problem-solving, critical thinking, and reasoning. These tasks may appeal to only some students, making them less engaging.

Research shows that learning styles don't significantly impact academic performance. Instead, educators should focus on diverse teaching methods to cater to individual needs and promote an inclusive and equitable educational environment.

The study reveals a more vital link between learning styles and academic performance as individuals age, with teaching durations and divisions having a moderate positive impact.

Based on the findings in this study and the conclusions drawn, the following are at this moment recommended:

Support teachers' professional development through workshops, seminars, and conferences, and offer scholarships, grants, or financial assistance to seek specialized training or higher degrees to enhance their abilities and add to the calibre of education.

Teachers should incorporate more visual aids and techniques like mind mapping in the educational process, especially for subjects where visual learning can be more effective. This recommendation is supported by the high percentage of visual (Spatial) learning styles contributing to academic performance.

Based on the research finding that learning styles do not significantly impact academic performance, teachers should shift their focus toward implementing diverse teaching methods. By adopting a more inclusive and adaptive teaching manner, teachers may produce a more captivating and productive learning environment for all students, ultimately promoting better academic outcomes.

The Visual (Spatial) Learning Style is also recommended for public school teachers to use to improve learners' academic performance.

Further research may be conducted to determine the impact of learners' learning styles on their academic performance from another perspective.

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